

**BASICS OF DEVELOPMENT OF TACTICAL AND
TECHNICAL SKILLS OF BOXERS**

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Annotation: Physical education as a necessary condition for the comprehensive development of a person is aimed at improving the physical and spiritual strength of a young person. Physical development and physical education of students is carried out in unity with mental, moral and aesthetic education. One of the main links in the physical education system in higher educational institutions is additional extracurricular activities in various sports; boxing occupies a special place among students.

Key words: boxing, students, sports training, training, battle tactics, boxing technique.

Introduction. Most higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan cultivate and develop this sport because it builds self-confidence in a young person, the ability to overcome difficulties and achieve goals, and teaches decency and nobility. Boxing is a courageous and very exciting sport [1, 2, 4]. It is one of the important ways of physical education for young people. The great popularity of boxing is explained by its entertainment value, the high emotional stress of wrestling and its diverse influence on a person's motor, mental and volitional qualities [3, 5]. Boxing fosters exactly those qualities that are extremely necessary for a young man at the beginning of his development as a person, personality, and specialist.

To achieve results in conditions of constant training and competition, it requires constant improvement of the athlete's technical and tactical skills [6, 9, 10].

At the same time, the level of technical readiness in most cases is achieved through a combination of technical training and targeted physical training. Currently, the most important problem in boxing is the long-term technical and tactical training and education of athletes at the stage of specialized basic training [7, 8, 11]. Unfortunately, little attention has been paid to this issue in wrestling theory; most studies have been conducted with high-class athletes.

Practice shows that for students in physical and sports education groups, the most common sports-oriented form of organizing physical education classes. This is evidenced by the results of a number of scientific studies. Thus, in the study of O.K. Amonturdiev, it is concluded that the organization of physical education classes for students based on students' independent choice of sports specialization is the most progressive form [12, 13]. According to scientists, it is this approach that stimulates students' interest in a particular sport and in the development of their physical abilities. The above problem determines the relevance of this work [14].

Systematic boxing exercises create a profound effect on the growing body. Through physical activity, the activity of all organs and systems is activated, the body's ability to mobilize functional capabilities and more economically perform muscle work increases.

It is necessary to know and take into account that exercises that develop strength mainly affect the development of bones and muscles, and endurance training mainly increases the capacity of the vegetative organs. In the process of adapting the body to muscle loads, changes occur in the activity of the endocrine glands. An increased supply of hormones to all tissues stimulates metabolic processes.

The result of sports training and the period of maintaining a high level of sports form in boxing depend on many factors, one of which is building a solid foundation for building up technical and tactical training and developing the athlete's special physical abilities. The lack of a training system in such a technically complex sport as boxing can lead to chaotic development of skills and a decrease in the versatility

of the athlete. And the highest criterion in determining a fighter's skill is his versatile and effective technical training.

Technical readiness is characterized by the degree to which an athlete has mastered a system of movements that meet the characteristics of a given sport and ensure the achievement of high results. Boxing is a sport with very complex and varied movement techniques. The fighting technique has more than one and a half million arsenal of basic techniques and their modifications, which result in complex technical and tactical actions (combinations and counter-techniques), elementary actions (movement, capture, unbalancing, belaying partners and self-insurance) [15, 16].

The first prerequisite for the formation of a wrestler's technical skill is the high quality of initial training in the technique of fighting, but when there are omissions in the technique, it is necessary to radically relearn [17].

At the stage of specialized basic training, the main place is occupied by general and auxiliary training, exercises in related sports are widely used, and their technique is improved. In the second half of this stage, training becomes more specialized. Here, as a rule, the main technical and tactical techniques are determined, and athletes begin to use them in fights. At this stage, means are widely used to increase the functional potential of the athlete's body without the use of a large amount of work, which is as close in nature to competitive activity as possible.

The high skill of an athlete largely depends on how he mastered the wrestling technique. The higher his technical training and the skillfully he masters various techniques, the greater success can be expected from a fight, sparring, or duel [3, 5]. All boxing techniques can be divided into ordinary and complex actions. The first includes various jerks, turns, and movements around the ring. The second includes defensive techniques and counter-techniques. The first and second have a certain tactical load, since any of the listed actions can be used as tactical. A boxer's tactical knowledge is an idea of techniques, types, forms of tactics and their use in the process of training and competition. Tactical skills - actions dictated by tactical

knowledge: predict the opponent's plan and the competitive battle situation; the ability to adjust your tactical plan during a fight [8]. Tactical skills are integral tactical actions implemented during training and competition. A boxer's tactical thinking is the ability to make the right tactical decisions under time pressure and high mental stress [1, 6, 7].

Tactical training of a boxer is the process of mastering sports tactics, its types, forms and means of their implementation in competitions and fights. The structure of tactical training in boxing consists of actions aimed at developing tactical knowledge, abilities, skills and thinking in general [5].

The objectives of tactical training at the stage of specialized basic training are to improve the skills of conducting fights with different opponents and to develop the skills to participate in important competitions. Tactical preparation for performing techniques, counter-techniques and combinations is studied; combat tactics; fighting technique. An analysis of the skill of opponents is carried out, the position in the standings is determined, and the distribution of forces is carried out [1, 3].

Boxing tactics should be understood as the art of using technical means, taking into account one's technical, tactical, moral, volitional and physical capabilities in battle with opponents of different styles and manners. A boxer's tactical maturity is determined by his combat experience. The more he meets experienced and strong athletes, the higher his tactical skill. Boxing tactics consist of an organic combination and timely use of tactical actions, which can be divided into three groups:

- preparatory actions;
- offensive actions;
- defensive actions.

Preparatory steps include:

- familiarization with the opponent's skill level, his style and manner of fighting;
- concealing one's intentions through deceptive actions;

- analysis and assessment of the enemy's actions, his style and manner of fighting, physical fitness, courage and determination, the ability to perform deceptive actions, the use of favorite techniques and behavior after receiving a blow;
- through maneuvering, creating positions convenient for attacks and counterattacks, the ability to keep the opponent at the required distance;
- determination of the opponent's speed and strength data [2, 4].

Offensive actions are reflected in attacks and counterattacks. Counterattacks can be counterattacks, repeated attacks, or in response to an opponent's counterattack.

Tactical plans may also include defensive actions. During quick attacks with a series of blows, the defending boxer tries to reliably cover his head with his hands in order to slightly tire his opponent with his somewhat passive actions. Carrying out the task with dodges and kicks, he finds out in which places the opponent opens up during attacks. After receiving a strong blow, the boxer tries to leave the fight or enter into close combat and block the opponent with passive actions in order to rest, recover, collect, prepare and choose an inconvenient moment for the opponent, then begin his own attack. Defensive actions are often used to divert the opponent's attention [2].

Conclusions. Boxing has a noticeable impact on the health, growth and development of the body of young men. The incidence of illness among students involved in boxing is much lower than that of their peers who are not involved in boxing. Boxing increases the body's resistance to the adverse influences of the external environment and is therefore a more important means of promoting health and preventing diseases. But if, with systematic training and rational selection of training loads, boxers exhibit high levels of immune reactivity, then with irregular training or excessive loads, the strength of nonspecific immunity decreases, which leads to a decrease in the body's resistance to infections. Student boxers differ from their peers by higher rates of physical development; when compared with students who do not engage in boxing, greater strength, lability and balance of nervous processes are noted.

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